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Department of Human Resource Management
Faculty of Management Studies

Rajarata University of Sri Lanka

AI AND HR TRANSFORMATION

AI and HR Transformation: Towards a Leadership Perspective

Artificial Intelligent leadership is an AI-driven leadership model that emphasizes the creation of intelligent technological leaders with machine learning, data analytics, and natural language processes who play roles and react like a leader in the organization context. That consists with capabilities such as, supporting the decision-making process for quality decisions, and planning the strategy, and enhancing operational efficiency.

But it can be identified as an effective leadership model when it blends with the human leadership models also. As a result of human nature, dealing with human is more complex for AIL to cope with their team members even blend with human qualities. Artificial intelligence knowledge and experiences are just leadership qualities that should have effective leadership emerge in the new technological era. There is a tendency for AIL approach become fail, if it does not have the ability to influence people toward the attainment of goals, and is absent from earning respect from the followers then it doesn't create effective leadership.

Furthermore, Artificial Intelligent Leadership (AIL) is a modern leadership model in the field of business management especially in the 4th revolutionary era. In the new technological era, AI-driven leadership is defined as a process of automating every function of leadership.

It shows the unique key characteristics rather than traditional leadership, selflessly, tirelessly, 24/7 work for the organization. Leadership is the one of main functions in management. From the management perspective, it is identified as leading an organization's limited resources toward its established objectives.

"AI-based leadership can be seen to drive more practices in the organization with new qualities such as robot process automation, data security, customer service, human resources, and cyber security."

As of today, business is running in the world with so many changes affected by economic, social, political, and technological. Therefore taking prompt actions to match the world changes with management aspects is pivotal and that emerged necessity of shifting the business landscape to the AIL approach. Business experts should look at it as an opportunity not a threat for the business. The management board room should be opened for these matters to decide whether we changed with the upgrade or not as soon as for future forecast.

In new era emphasizes that leading limited resources of the organization assist with AI driven leadership is very impressed than ever. HRM, Finance, Marketing, Operation, entrepreneurship, and Engineering have been connected with AI technologies to manage the basic functions of management: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling limited resources with features of creativity, flexible and innovation.

When it comes to HR, AI leadership has become a mutual friend of human leadership. Human leaders should embrace it as a culture. Human resources are only active resources in every organization and they lead and make decisions regarding allocation of other factors.

AI Leadership is a technological structure, it cannot be emotional like a human leader. Organizations should never throw away human leadership.

AI Leadership can be built by upgrading human leadership with AI technologies. Never does it imply an organization practicing robotic leadership.

As employee are our first customers, we must appreciate them in the way they feel. At this point, AIL is failed to do this as it is not associated with humanity in some points. AIL is not more intelligent than human leadership, that because AI Leadership is always analyze and solve the problems which have already identify as an errors. It should applies only for pre-determined errors as preventive strategy. As my view of point, AIL has failed in some points when it tries to imitate or follow human behaviors. some practices, which can be generated through AI HR leadership model are given below.

Cyber Attack: “Conventional or human leadership approaches are not in better position to avoid a cyber-attacks”. That means develop the AIL would be better to identify risk associated factors to avoid same threats on digital platforms as in today all businesses communication and information sharing have been extended on that.

Data Accuracy: In the technologically driven era, business decisions are being taken using solely digital data. Responsibility for the accuracy and quality of data has right on AIL hands. Therefore leveraging AIL approach would help to make better decision readily.

Customer Services: when it comes to the customers, they are our king and we should need to satisfy them in order to get positive feedbacks from them. They are always seeking for product or service with new technology and that can be achieved with support from the AIL.

Artificial Leadership qualities: Such as, data analysis, employee engagement, automation, fostering culture of innovation, predictive analytics. In the modernistic technology era, business uses new technology to simplify the day-to-day workload of humans and but it could not be implemented solely with technological support.

It should be required human participation also. Hence, the AIL approach for HRM is not a perfect robotic leader. It must contain artificial leadership plus human leadership. Because at some times machine intelligence takes decisions more not productive than human intelligence.

As an example: when applying leadership for acquiring and retaining talent within an organization, it is better if there is a combination of AI leadership with human leadership. AI leadership performs best in shortlisting and evaluating performance levels of team members using AI tools but it failed to identify emotional personality characteristics of the team members.

Due to the environment's unpredictability, that would require potential AI knowledgeable human leadership strategy to survive in the environment for reaching sustainable human resource development. Collaboration among AIL and HL approaches will grab future opportunities and overcome challenges but not only that also when application of AIL for HR management perspective, there is a severe question that has emerged: how could artificial intelligence-driven machine leadership replace humans?

Therefore, the immediate practice of machine leadership beyond human leadership model is pivotal for ensuring sustainability of business growth in the future.

Mr. RD Weerasinghe
Assistant Lecturer
Department of Human Resource Management
Faculty of Commerce & Management Studies
University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka